

Synthesis of some new 2,4,6-trisubstituted phenyl pyrimidines using 4-nitro and 4-fluorophenacyldimethylsulfonium bromides with aromatic aldehydes

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Abstract : 4-Nitrophenacyldimethylsulfonium bromide and 4-fluorophenacyldimethylsulfonium bromide have been prepared by the reaction of dimethyl sulfide with 4-substitutedphenacyl bromide in benzene at reflux temperature under nitrogen atmosphere. These sulfonium salts on treatment with NaOH gave 4-nitrophenacylidenedimethylsulfurane and 4-fluorophenacylidenedimethylsulfurane. The reaction of these sulfonium salts and sulfuranes with various aromatic aldehydes is carried out in presence of ammonium acetate and acetic acid at reflux in an atmosphere of nitrogen to give 2,4,6-triarylpyrimidines in 35-80% yields. Ammonium acetate in acetic acid was used as aza cyclization agent. The structures of new pyrimidines were confirmed on the basis of IR and NMR spectral data.

Keywords : Aldehyde, pyrimidine, ylides, sulfonium salts.

Pyridinium, phosphonium, arsonium and isoquinolinium ylides have gained considerable importance in the synthesis of acyclic, cyclic and heterocyclic compounds¹. As reported earlier sulfonium salts and sulfuranes are also better potential reagents than corresponding salts and ylides of V-th group elements for the synthesis of cyclic and heterocyclic system². Further extensions of reaction of sulfonium ylides leading to the pyrimidine nucleus seems to be pertinent with a view to test the domain of applicability of sulfonium ylides. In the present investigation 4-nitrophenacyldimethylsulfonium bromide and 4-fluorophenacyldimethylsulfonium bromide as well as their corresponding sulfuranes have been coupled with a wide range of aromatic aldehydes in the presence of ammonium acetate and acetic acid at reflux temperature leading to ring closure to form pyrimidine nucleus.

Results and discussion

Reaction of dimethylsulfide with 4-nitrophenacyl bromide and 4-fluorophenacyl bromide in benzene at reflux temperature gave 4-nitrophenacyl bromide (**1a**) 4-fluorophenacyldimethylsulfonium bromide (**1b**) in fair to good yields. The structure of sulfonium salts (**1a-b**) were confirmed by comparison of melting points of salts with those reported in the literature³ and by spectral data. The IR spectra of salts (**1a-b**) showed a characteristic absorption band due to C-O stretching vibrations in the region 1670-

1690 cm^{-1} for carbonyl group. The diagnostic absorption bands in the region 3300-3000 cm^{-1} were observed due to C-H stretching vibrations of methylene group attached to sulfur atom⁴.

The treatment of these salts (**1a-b**) with aqueous sodium hydroxide/potassium carbonate gave 4-nitrophenacyldimethylsulfurane (**2a**) and 4-fluorophenacyldimethylsulfurane (**2b**) which are highly unstable. The reaction was, therefore, carried out by generating the ylide

Scheme 1

intermediates (**2a-b**) *in situ* from the corresponding salts (**1a-b**). Heating the mixture of sulfonium salts (**1a-b**) with substituted benzaldehyde (**3a-l**) in presence of ammonium acetate and glacial acetic acid at reflux temperature gave 2,4,6-triarylpyrimidines (**5a-l**, **6a-l**) in 35–80% yields (Scheme 1).

Further attempts were made to synthesize symmetrical pyrimidines having identical substituents at 2,4,6-positions. For this purpose 4-nitrophenacyldimethylsulfonium bromide (**1a**) with 4-nitrobenzaldehyde and 4-fluorophenacyldimethylsulfonium bromide (**1b**) with 4-fluorobenzaldehyde were heated in a mixture of ammonium

Table 1. Physical properties of 2,4,6-triarylpyrimidines (**5a-l**, **6a-l**)

Compd.	X	Y	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Recrystn. solvent	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
5a	4-NO ₂	H	45	110–112	A	74.02 (74.05)	4.35 (4.37)	12.20 (12.24)
b	4-NO ₂	4-CH ₃	40	96–98	B	75.61 (75.59)	4.93 (4.98)	11.04 (11.02)
c	4-NO ₂	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	45	120–122	A	71.03 (71.07)	5.67 (4.98)	15.99 (15.95)
d	4-NO ₂	4-OCH ₃	60	128–130	C	69.70 (69.73)	4.62 (4.60)	10.14 (10.07)
e	4-NO ₂	4-Cl	65	78–80	A	62.54 (62.56)	3.04 (3.08)	10.07 (10.05)
f	4-NO ₂	4-Br	55	86–98	B	55.76 (55.81)	2.71 (2.75)	8.82 (8.88)
g	4-NO ₂	4-F	65	110–112	C	67.80 (67.87)	3.36 (3.34)	9.27 (9.26)
h	4-NO ₂	3,4- <i>di</i> (OCH ₃)	48	122–124	A	70.40 (70.59)	5.68 (5.64)	9.42 (9.48)
i	4-NO ₂	4-NO ₂	80	132–134	C	59.55 (59.59)	2.90 (2.93)	15.82 (15.80)
6a	4-F	H	48	98–100	D	80.92 (80.98)	4.62 (4.60)	11.62 (11.64)
b	4-F	4-CH ₃	45	112–114	B	81.34 (75.59)	5.37 (4.98)	7.92 (11.02)
c	4-F	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	41	124–126	C	75.70 (75.72)	6.06 (6.07)	13.52 (13.59)
d	4-F	4-OCH ₃	42	130–320	A	78.42 (78.47)	5.15 (5.17)	7.64 (7.62)
e	4-F	4-Cl	50	76–78	C	66.80 (66.84)	3.26 (3.29)	7.05 (5.79)
f	4-F	4-Br	55	88–90	A	57.80 (57.85)	2.67 (2.69)	5.75 (5.79)
g	4-F	4-F	60	108–110	B	72.90 (72.93)	3.52 (3.59)	7.70 (7.73)
h	4-F	3,4- <i>di</i> (OCH ₃)	50	124–126	A	69.94 (69.99)	5.13 (5.15)	6.24 (6.28)
i	4-F	4-NO ₂	45	128–130	C	63.42 (63.46)	3.10 (3.12)	13.42 (13.46)

A=CH₃OH : CHCl₃, B=C₆H₆ : CHCl₃, C=C₃H₅N : CH₃OH

acetate and glacial acetic acid to give corresponding symmetrical pyrimidines viz. 2,4,6-tri-(4-nitrophenyl) pyrimidine (**5i**) and 2,4,6-tri-(4-fluorophenyl) pyrimidine (**6g**) respectively in 60% and 65% yields (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

The reaction takes place through Mannich type reaction. The methylene group of salt (**1a-b**) with aromatic aldehydes (**3a-l**) in presence of ammonium acetate forms Mannich base sulfonium to form sulfonium salt (**4a**) which, in turn, undergoes condensation with another molecule of benzaldehyde in presence of ammonia to form sulfonium salt intermediate (**4b**). The later, undergoes elimination of dimethylsulfonium hydrobromide to form 2,4,6-triarylpyrimidines (**5a-l**, **6a-l**).

A number of 2,4,6-triarylpyrimidine (**5a-l**) and (**6a-l**) synthesized by the above route are listed in Table 1. All the pyrimidines gave satisfactory elemental and spectral analysis. The IR spectral data showed (Table 2) characteristic absorption bands in the region 3100–3000 cm^{-1} which were assigned due to C–H stretching mode of pyrimidine ring. The bands in the region 1600–1500 cm^{-1} were due to interaction between C=C and C=N vibrations of the ring. The NMR spectra (Table 3) of pyrimidines showed pyrimidyl protons at C₅–H in the range δ 6.60–6.80 and aromatic protons at δ 6.60–8.40.

Experimental

All the reagents were obtained from commercial source (E. Merck, B.D.H., Sisco etc.). Starting materials 4-nitrophenacylbromide and 4-fluorophenacylbromide were prepared according to the procedure reported in literature⁵.

Table 2. IR data (KBr) (cm^{-1}) 2,4,6-triarylpyrimidines (**5a-i**, **6a-i**)

Compd.	IR data (KBr) (cm^{-1})				
	ν C–H	ν C=C	ν C–N	ϕ C–H	ν C–nNO ₂
5a	3110	1605	1510	995	1555, 1325
b	3085	1615	1525	990	1575, 1330
c	3105	1605	1510	995	1580, 1335
d	3115	1610	1520	992	1585, 1335
e	3060	1608	1505	990	1580, 1340
f	3110	1595	1500	1000	1575, 1320
g	3080	1598	1505	1005	1570, 1325
h	3108	1605	1510	1000	1580, 1330
i	3070	1610	1510	1005	1575, 1320
6a	3090	1600	1505	998	
b	3105	1605	1510	1005	
c	3100	1615	1500	992	
d	3065	1598	1500	1000	
e	3080	1605	1510	1010	
f	3100	1615	1505	992	
g	3105	1614	1505	995	
h	3080	1600	1500	998	
i	3095	1608	1505	990	

ν = Stretching vibrations; ϕ = out-of-plane deformation of hydrogen attached to aromatic nucleus (**5a-l**, **6a-l**).

Preparation of 4-substituted phenacyldimethyl sulfonium bromide (**1a-b**) :

A solution of 100 mmol of 4-nitrophenacyl bromide and 100 mmol of dimethyl sulfide in 100 ml of anhydrous acetone was stirred for 6–8 h at room temperature in an atmosphere of nitrogen gave solid mass which was filtered, washed twice with acetone and crystallized from benzene pet. as detailed below.

4-Nitrophenacyldimethyl sulfonium bromide (**1a**), yellow coloured microcrystals m.p. 150–152 °C (lit.² m.p. 152–154 °C); IR data (KBr) 1680 (C=O), 1570, 1330 cm^{-1} (C–NO₂); NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.30 (6H, s, di-CH₃), 5.50 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.30–7.90 (4H, m, ArH).

4-Fluorophenacyldimethyl sulfonium bromide (**1b**), white colourless microcrystals m.p. 140–142 °C (lit.³ m.p. 142–144 °C); IR data (KBr) 3100 (ArH), 1675 cm^{-1} (C=O); NMR (CDCl₃) δ 3.26 (6H, s, di-CH₃), 8.45 (2H, s, CH₂), 7.25–7.85 (4H, m, ArH).

Table 3. NMR (CDCl₃) data of 2,4,6-triarylpyrimidines (**5a-i**, **6a-i**)

Compd.	δ (ppm)	No. of protons	Assignment of protons
5a	6.65s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
	6.85–6.88m	14H	Ar-H
b	6.25s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
	2.35s	6H	di-CH ₃
	6.95–8.20m	12H	Ar-H
c	6.65s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
	3.95s	12H	di-(OCH ₃)
	6.75–7.85m	12H	Ar-H
d	6.66s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
	3.85s	6H	di-(OCH ₃)
	6.95–8.35m	12H	Ar-H
e	6.78s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
	7.0–8.25m	12H	Ar-H
f	5.80s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
	6.95–8.20m	12H	Ar-H
g	6.75s	1H	Phy (C ₅ -H)
	7.10–8.35m	12H	Ar-H
h	6.65s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
	3.95d (<i>J</i> 6 Hz)	12H	di-(3,4-di-OCH ₃)
	6.85–7.85m	10H	Ar-H
i	6.75s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
	7.05–8.35m	12H	Ar-H
6a	6.60s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
	6.75–7.95m	14H	Ar-H
b	6.65s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
	2.50s	6H	di-CH ₃
	6.85–8.15m	12H	Ar-H
c	6.70s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
	2.95s	12H	di-(OCH ₃)
	6.85–7.15m	12H	Ar-H
d	6.60s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
	3.95s	6H	di-(OCH ₃)
e	6.95–8.35m	12H	Ar-H
	6.75s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
f	7.05–8.35m	12H	Ar-H
	6.80s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
g	7.15–8.45m	12H	Ar-H
	6.85s	1H	Phy (C ₅ -H)
h	7.10–8.35m	12H	Ar-H
	6.65s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
i	3.85d (<i>J</i> 6 Hz)	12H	di-(3,4-di-OCH ₃)
	6.95–8.28m	10H	Ar-H
	6.70s	1H	PyH (C ₅ -H)
i	7.10–8.35m	12H	Ar-H

s = singlet; m = multiplet; d = doublet

Preparation of 2,4,6-triarylpyrimidines (5a-l**, **6a-l**) :****General procedure :**

A mixture of 3 mmol 4-substituted phenacyldimethylsulfonium bromide (**1a-b**) and 6 mmol of aromatic aldehyde (**3**) and 3 g of ammonium acetate in 50 ml of glacial acetic acid was stirred at room temperature. The mixture was then poured in ice cold water (50 ml) which was continually stirred. The solid mass was precipitated, filtered and washed twice with water and then with methanol and dried. The product, was chromatographed over neutral alumina and chlorform : pet. ether as mobile solvent gave crystalline products which were recrystallised from suitable solvent to give 2,4,6-triarylpyrimidine (**5a-l**) and (**6a-l**) in good yields as computed in Table 1.

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